

Use of infrared spectroscopy for a sampling study of waste wood samples in a panel board industry

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Waste wood (WW) includes wood or wood-containing materials from different sources, i.e., packaging, construction, and demolition activities; furniture and industrial sector (Edo et al., 2016). WW is considered a valuable material especially because its efficient utilization can aid in contributing to climate change mitigation (Röder and Thornley, 2018). In particular, it can help in reducing greenhouse gas emissions when it is being recycled for the panel board industry. However, even treating it as a secondary resource for energy recovery instead of a waste to dispose of will mitigate climate change. This more efficient utilization of WW is in accordance with the European policy and the Waste Framework Directive that promotes the circular economy and reuse and recycle over the disposal in landfill.

Considering the heterogeneity and chemical complexity of WW (Huron et al., 2017), an assessment of product composition is necessary before deciding its most appropriate use on the basis of quality attributes. To this aim, a sampling study was carried out in order to investigate the variation in samples properties and ensure reliable and representative results. A set of WW samples have been collected in a panel board industry located in the northern part of Italy. The samples have been analysed ground and in their original form by means of spectroscopic techniques. In addition, they have been analysed both with their original moisture content directly in the panel board industry and after a stabilization process (moisture equilibrium). The collected data have been investigated using multivariate data analysis techniques to determine the optimal sampling procedure in terms of frequency of sampling and number of replicates to perform. The outcomes provide preliminary indications about the sampling procedure to carry out in order to collect representative samples and get reliable results, as well as the variability inherent in WW materials.

Keywords: heterogeneity, NIR, multivariate data analysis, circular economy, wood reuse

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